

Spectrophotometric Determination of Selenium in Soil and Alloys

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Manuscript received 27 July 1987, revised 9 February 1988, accepted 22 April 1988

A rapid method for spectrophotometric micro determination of selenium using propericiazine has been reported. A red radical cation is formed at 7–9 M HCl which absorbs maximum at 515 nm and stable for 2 h. Beer's law is obeyed for upto 3.5 μg selenium per ml. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $3.736 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.002 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The optimum reaction conditions and other analytical parameters are evaluated. The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and can be used for the determination of selenium content in soil and alloys.

SELENIUM and its compounds are commonly used in electronic, ceramics, pigment and steel industries. It is essential for healthy animal development¹ and the intake of selenium bearing plants causes chronic selenosis. It has been found that cruciferous plants accumulate much more selenium than other vegetables². Hence considerable effort has been directed towards measuring selenium in soils and plant materials.

Because of its commercial as well as biological importance, a wide variety of reagents³⁻⁶ have been proposed for its spectrophotometric determination. These methods, however, are intricate, time consuming or are not sensitive enough to deal with soil samples. During a systematic study on phenothiazine⁷⁻¹⁰ it was found that propericiazine (PPC) forms a red radical cation with selenium(IV) at room temperature. In this paper, a detailed study of the selenium(IV)-PPC system has been carried out and a method is proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of selenium(IV) in soil and alloys.

Experimental

A Beckman DB spectrophotometer with 1 cm cells was employed. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Standard selenium(IV) solution Selenium dioxide was dissolved in water (500 ml) containing concentrated HCl (5 ml). The selenium content of the solution was determined by the gravimetric method¹¹. A working solution ($10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by diluting the standard solution.

Propericiazine (PPC) solution: PPC (Bayer, A.G.) was checked for its purity volumetrically using ceric sulphate¹². A 0.2% solution was prepared by dissolving PPC in water and kept in amber coloured bottle.

Procedure: An aliquot of selenium(IV) solution containing upto 87.50 μg was transferred into a 25 ml flask and 10 M HCl (20 ml) and 0.2% PPC (1 ml) were added. The solution was made upto the mark and allowed 15 min for complete colour development. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 515 nm against the reagent blank.

Procedure of the determination of selenium in soil samples: A known weight of selenium was mixed with soil, fused with 1:1 sodium carbonate and potassium nitrate mixture in a nickel crucible and extracted with water. The filtrate of the extract was treated with 10 M HCl (20 ml) and then heated to expel chlorine and oxides of nitrogen. The solution was further diluted with water to give a stock solution of 10 μg of Se per ml. An aliquot of the stock solution was passed through the cation-exchange resin Amberlite IR-120H to remove the iron present in soil. The selenium content was determined from the elutant, which is almost free from iron following the procedure described above.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary investigations were carried out to establish the optimum conditions for the formation of the selenium-PPC species. These showed that selenium(IV) reacts with PPC at room temperature in HCl medium to form a red species, which is

believed to be a radical cation^{13,14} $C_{21}H_{28}OSN_8^+$. Constant absorbance values were obtained 15 min after adding the reagent to the selenium solution, which remained stable for 2 h.

Spectral characteristics: Absorption spectra of radical cation in HCl exhibited maximum absorbance at 515 nm. The reagent blank exhibited negligible absorption at this wavelength.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity: Beer's law was obeyed for upto $3.5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of selenium. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $3.736 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.002 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The optimum concentration range for the effective spectrophotometric determination of selenium, as evaluated by Ringbom's method¹⁵ was $0.5-3.0 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The standard deviation and relative error were ± 0.0028 and $\pm 0.842\%$ respectively.

Effect of variables :

Acidity: Maximum intensity of the red colour was achieved in $7-9 M$ HCl. Below $7 M$ acid concentration the colour development was slow and at a higher concentration the reagent slowly oxidised. Acid concentration of $8 M$ was chosen for all subsequent work.

Reagent concentration: It was found that at least a 10-fold molar excess of the reagent was required to obtain maximum and constant absorbance. However, a 15-fold molar excess of the reagent was always used to ensure complete reaction. There was no appreciable change in the absorbance or colour of the radical cation if the order of addition of reactants was varied.

Effect of diverse ions: The extent of interference by the cations usually associated with selenium and common anions were determined by measuring the absorbance of a solution containing $2 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of selenium and various amounts of diverse ions. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance was considered tolerable for the determination of selenium in soil and alloys.

The tolerance limits of diverse ions in the determination of $4 \mu\text{g Se}^{IV}$ per ml are as follows (figures in parenthesis represent tolerance limit in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$): Ba^{++} and Zn^{++} (4000), Al^{+++} and Bi^{+++} (1500), Cd^{++} (2500), Ca^{++} (1500), Co^{++} (100), Cr^{+++} (250), Hg^{++} (400), Mn^{++} and Ni^{++} (600), Pb (3000), Fe^{+++} (1800), Cu^{++} (10), Te^{IV} (60), UO_2^{++} (800), Rh^{+++} (50), fluoride (2000), chloride (3000), bromide (4000), nitrate (250), sulphate (5000), phosphate (1600), oxalate (200), acetate (4500), tartrate (8000), citrate (5000) and EDTA (5000); in case of Fe^{+++} , iron was removed by passing through Amberlite IR-120H resin, and in case of Cu^{++} , 1% EDTA (1 ml) was used as masking agent. The results show that 30-fold excess of tellurium, a large excess of base metals and anions do not interfere. Upto 1.8 mg ml^{-1} of iron(III) was

tolerated but excess amount had to be removed by passing the solution through the cation-exchanger Amberlite IR-120H.

Determination of selenium in soil and alloys: In order to confirm the usefulness of the proposed method it was applied to the determination of selenium in soil samples and synthetic mixtures corresponding to selenium alloys of Se-Fe (42-51% Fe), Se-Hg (71%Hg) and Se-Pb (62% Pb) were prepared, and the selenium content was determined. The result are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SELENIUM IN SOIL AND SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sample	Se added $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Se found* $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Standard deviation	
Soil	0.60	0.58	0.002	
	1.50	1.47	0.002	
	3.00	2.95	0.001	
Alloy				
	Fe-Se ^a	0.50	0.49	0.002
		1.00	0.98	0.002
2.00		1.97	0.001	
Hg-Se	0.50	0.49	0.002	
	1.50	1.49	0.002	
	2.50	2.51	0.002	
Pb-Se	0.80	0.81	0.003	
	1.60	1.62	0.002	
	2.40	2.42	0.001	

*Average of five determinations. ^aPassed through cation-exchange resin Amberlite IR-120 H.

The proposed method offers a simple and accurate procedure for the determination of selenium in soil and alloys

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